

Department
for Environment
Food & Rural Affairs

Consolidate, utilise and curate existing datasets for ash genomics

Final Report to Centre for Forest Protection for Pilot Year (April 2021-July 2022)

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Executive summary

This report is for a project funded in the pilot year of the Centre for Forest Protection, plus a four-month extension, ending on 31 July 2022. Previous sequencing work funded by Defra identified thousands of single-nucleotide polymorphisms associated with ash dieback resistance in ash trees from field trials. With Defra funding we also previously generated whole genome sequence data for a natural population of ash in Surrey. In the present project we followed up this work as follows. (1) The population re-sequencing data from a natural ash population in Surrey was analysed, showing evidence for the increase of alleles associated with ash dieback resistance at many of these loci. Thus natural selection seems to be increasing the population's resistance to ash dieback. Our data also show that genomic estimates of breeding values of parent trees are more accurate than

phenotypic estimates of parents' health. A manuscript reporting this work has been submitted to a scientific journal for publication. (2) Public accessibility of ash genomic data was improved. (3) A new, more complete, genome assembly for an eastern European ash, built by our Polish collaborators, has been annotated. (4) Data from the field trial has been reanalysed using this new assembly. This identified a larger, partially different, set of genes associated with ash dieback resistance compared to the previous analysis, which used a more fragmented reference genome assembly from a British tree. (5) Using the new assembly, structural genomic variants were genotyped in the field trial data, with preliminary analysis indicating that some of these are associated with ash dieback resistance. These results underline the need for a pan-genome reference for European ash. This work is now being followed up by a project funded under the 2022-2025 Centre for Forest Protection research programme, entitled: "Transforming ash genomics: a pan-genome resource for improved understanding of ash dieback resistance".

Background

Ash Dieback

Ash dieback (ADB) is projected to cost the UK £7.6 billion by the end of this decade (Hill et al. 2019). It directly threatens 45 obligate ash-associated species and removes an alternate host for species relying on other threatened trees, reducing woodland ecosystem resilience (Mitchell et al. 2022). A "deeper and more robust understanding of the genetic basis...for tolerance to ADB" has been identified as a key research need for the future in the Defra strategy on ash research. Robustly identifying the genetic basis of resistance will enhance predictions of whether ash populations can adapt to this threat and inform potential breeding programmes, ultimately assisting the long-term survival of native ash - a policy aim of the same strategy.

Previous Ash Dieback Genomics

Defra has previously funded work sequencing ADB resistant vs. susceptible pools of ash trees from 15 different native seed zones from the UK and Europe (published in Stocks et al. 2019). A genome-wide association study was performed using this data that identified 3,149 single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) associated with ADB resistance. This data

was used to train a genomic prediction model that was able to predict the health status of individual trees with 67% accuracy (Stocks et al. 2019).

In 2019, Defra funded further sequencing work on a natural ash population. Five hundred and eighty ash trees with known ADB disease status from a natural woodland in England were sequenced.

A new reference assembly for *F. excelsior* has recently been made publicly available by our Polish collaborators (FRAX-001; NCBI genome_assembly_id=1654294) which shows much greater contiguity than the previous assembly, with an N50 value of 35.6Mb compared with 103.9kb for the BATG-0.5 assembly. The increased contiguity of this reference genome will potentially increase the number of ADB resistance variants it is possible to identify from the field trial data.

Structural Variants

We have not previously investigated the role of structural variants (SVs) in ash dieback resistance. SVs are genomic regions that differ in presence, abundance, position or orientation between individuals. They are associated with significant agricultural traits (Fiol et al. 2021; Guo et al. 2020; Sun et al. 2020; Pinosio et al. 2016) and potentially explain a proportion of missing trait heritability (Manolio et al. 2009). While some significant SVs may impact a nearby detectable SNP, many could be missed by SNP-focused analyses (Zhou et al. 2019). Furthermore, SVs may impact phenotypes more strongly than SNPs, by producing large rearrangements in regulatory regions, or altering expression levels by modifying gene copy numbers (Alonge et al. 2020). Trait variance explained by SVs has been found to be complementary to (Hämälä et al. 2021; Guo et al. 2020), or exceed (Dorant et al. 2020), that explained by SNPs. Notably, enrichment of disease resistance genes in SVs has been found in multiple tree species (Pinosio et al. 2016; Sun et al. 2020; Prunier, Caron, and MacKay 2017; Prunier et al. 2019; Hämälä et al. 2021; Jiao and Schneeberger 2020). The increased contiguity of the FRAX-001 linear genome assembly could facilitate investigation of this additional source of genomic variation in the genetic basis of ADB resistance.

Aims and Objectives

1. To analyse the natural ash population re-sequencing data and submit a manuscript on it to a scientific journal.

2. To make ash data available on Zenodo and upload short-read sequencing data from the natural population to public databases.
3. To annotate the new FRAX-001 assembly by both i) identifying the position of genes annotated in the BATG-0.5 assembly using genomic liftover and ii) performing *de novo* annotation.
4. To perform a new genome-wide association study (GWAS) of the previously published field trial data on the FRAX-001 assembly.
5. To genotype for the first-time structural variants in the field trial data using the FRAX-001 assembly and identify whether any of these i) are significantly associated with ADB resistance ii) identify different sets of genes to those identified using SNPs.

Methods

Analysis of a natural ash population

The methods used in the analysis of sequence data from the natural ash population can be found in the submitted manuscript.

Increasing the public accessibility of ash genomics data

Data previously hosted only on the ashgenome.org website were made available in an Ash community on Zenodo.

The data from the natural ash population were made available on the ENA short read archive.

Re-annotating ash reference genome sequences

Annotation liftover from BATG-0.5 assembly

The flo pipeline (Pracana et al. 2017) was used to identify corresponding sequences and transfer annotations from the BATG-0.5 assembly to the FRAX-001 assembly. Default parameters were used, with BLAT options of `-tilesize=12` and `-minIdentity=98`.

De novo annotation

Repetitive elements in the FRAX-001 assembly were identified with RepeatModeler 2.0 (Flynn et al., 2020). These repeat sequences were combined with repetitive elements previously identified in *Fraxinus excelsior* (BATG-0.5, (Sollars et al. 2017), then provided to RepeatMasker 4.1.1 (Tarailo-Graovac and Chen 2009). Gene annotations were predicted

using BRAKER v2.1.5 (Brůna et al. 2021) using existing RNA sequencing data from multiple tissues and also previously identified gene models from *F. excelsior* (BATG-0.5)(Sollars et al. 2017). Genes were filtered by gFACs v1.1.2 for gene structure (Caballero and Wegrzyn 2019). Genes were filtered if they met the following criteria: CDS size less than 300 bp, exon and intron sizes of less than 9 bp, inframe stop codons, and/or lack of start or stop codons. Genes were next filtered by EnTAP v0.9.1 based on predicted function (Hart et al. 2020). For EnTAP, genes were compared against the Swissprot and TrEMBL plant protein databases and the EggNOG gene family database. Genes kept by EnTAP were again filtered by gFACs, yielding the final list of gene models. Transfer RNA (tRNA) were predicted using tRNAscan-SE version 2.0.5 on default settings (Chan et al. 2021). Ribosomal DNA (rDNA) locations were predicted using the program RNAmmer v1.2 (Lagesen et al. 2007).

Re-analysis of previous ash dieback GWAS datasets using new reference assemblies

Cleaned reads from each of the 30 pools from the previously generated GWAS datasets (Stocks et al. 2019) were mapped to the FRAX-001 assembly using bwa mem v0.7.17 (Li 2013). PCR duplicates and reads with mapping quality <20 were removed using samtools v1.9 (Li et al. 2009). Scaffolds unable to be placed on one of the 23 chromosomes were removed. Samtools was used to produce a pileup file with a maximum depth of 8,000 for inputting into Popoolation2 (Kofler, Pandey, and Schlötterer 2011). A Genome-Wide Association Study (GWAS) was performed with a Cochran-Mantel-Haenszel test using the cmh-test.pl utility in Popoolation2, with a minimum count of 15, a minimum coverage of 40 and a maximum coverage of 3,000. SNPs significantly associated with ash dieback were defined as those with a p-value < 1×10^{-13} as in (Stocks et al. 2019).

Analysis of the contribution of structural variants to ash dieback resistance

SVs were identified using a modified version of the method developed by (Schridder, Hahn, and Begun 2016; North et al. 2020). BAM files generated for the GWAS were merged across all pools from the field trials (Stocks et al. 2019). A modified version of step1e from

(North et al. 2020) was used to identify “everted” read pairs that can be the result of a tandem duplication in the sequenced genome which is absent in the reference genome. Step2e was run with a minimum read depth of 75 and a maximum insert size of 612bp to identify clusters of reads that may represent the start and the end of a tandem repeat. Cluster start and end locations were defined as between the 10th and 90th percentiles of the start and end mapping locations respectively of the supporting reads. Clusters with a start or end region larger than 2kb, or a distance of more than 50kb between the start and end, were discarded. Clusters with overlapping start positions were merged, but if the ends did not overlap both clusters were discarded to avoid complex nested SVs. The remaining cluster start/end locations were used to genotype individual pools. Samtools was used to identify “everted” reads that mapped within the start/end locations of each cluster, numbers of which were used as a proxy for the tandem duplicate allele frequency within a pool. The number of properly paired reads falling within these same locations were used as a proxy for the frequency of individuals lacking the tandem duplicate. These frequencies were calculated for all clusters across each pool. These values were used to perform a Cochran-Mantel-Haenszel test using the `mantelhaen.test` function in R.

Findings

Analysis of dataset from natural ash woodland

These findings are in a manuscript entitled:

“Genomic evidence of natural selection for ash dieback resistance”

The abstract of this manuscript is as follows:

Large changes in quantitative traits through small shifts in allele frequencies at many genetic loci driven by natural selection lie at the heart of the neo-Darwinian synthesis but are hard to fully demonstrate in the wild. The spread of a natural pathogen into a new host population containing standing genetic variation for quantitative resistance provides an opportunity to demonstrate such shifts occurring in real time. The invasive fungal pathogen (*Hymenoscyphus fraxineus*) causes ash dieback disease in European ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*) populations. The disease is frequently lethal, but larger trees persist longer, often with reduced reproductive output. Here, using whole genome resequencing of an infected natural ash tree population in England, we measure allele frequencies at 7985 single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) previously associated with resistance to the pathogen.

The average genetic merit for resistance of trees established after the start of the epidemic, calculated as Genomic Estimated Breeding Values (GEBV) from the 7985 loci, was higher than that of related adults from the pre-epidemic generation. We estimate that, to produce a GEBV shift of this magnitude, would require truncation selection eliminating at least 13% of the juvenile population. Even this rapid rate of change under natural selection may be insufficient for evolutionary rescue of European ash populations, but change could be accelerated by a breeding programme informed by genomic selection. To this end, we show that for predicting the health of their offspring, the GEBVs of parent trees perform better than a phenotypic assessment of the ash dieback damage parent trees have suffered.

A copy of this manuscript has been submitted to Defra along with this report. A pre-print has also been posted publicly here:

<https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2022.08.01.502033v1>. The manuscript has been submitted to a leading journal, and may not be publicised until published in a journal.

Increasing the public accessibility of ash genomics data

Data previously hosted only on the ashgenome.org website were made available on Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/communities/ash-tree-genome-analysis-fraxinus-species/>

The data from the natural ash population were made available on the ENA short read archive under accession PRJEB44697 (ERP128769).

Re-annotating ash reference genome sequences

Of the 38,949 genes identified in the BATG assembly (based on a British ash tree), the liftover identified 22,532 of these in the FRAX-001 assembly (based on a Polish ash tree). A further 7,448 were split in the new assembly and 5,636 partially deleted. 3,333 genes in the BATG assembly were not found in the FRAX-001 assembly. Of the 56 genes near SNPs significantly associated with ADB resistance in Stocks et al. (2019), 19 were identified in the liftover with an additional 11 split and 10 partially deleted, with 6 missing in the new assembly. Further refinement of the liftover may identify additional genes from the previous assembly in the new assembly, but it is likely that a substantial number of genes vary in their presence/absence between these British and Polish genomes. A pan-genome, a reference genome that combines data from genetically diverse individuals, will more

accurately identify the full complement of genes in *F. excelsior* and which are involved in ADB resistance.

The *de novo* annotation of the FRAX-001 assembly identified a total repeat content of 58.90%. Like most characterized plant genomes, long terminal repeats (LTRs) were the most commonly identified repetitive elements (21.92%), primarily from the Ty1/Copia (11.74%) and Gypsy/DIRS1 (8.75%) families (Baucom et al., 2009). Gene annotation yielded an initial set of 58,070 gene predictions that were further filtered by structural and functional annotation to a set of 41,355 high-confidence gene models. Almost all high-confidence genes (40,953; 99.03%) are located on the 23 chromosome sequences. The majority of high-quality genes were annotated with a sequence similarity match to a protein database (29,296) and assignment to an eggNOG gene family (41,346). In total, 34,783 genes were assigned at least one gene ontology (GO) term and 10,034 have at least one pathway assignment from KEGG. Annotation of tRNAs identified 789 candidate loci located on all 23 pseudomolecules as well as in 7 unplaced scaffolds. A total of 144 ribosomal RNA (rRNA) genes were identified, most of which were found on chromosome 2 (73; 50.69%) and scaffold 244 (25; 17.36%).

Re-analysis of previous ash dieback GWAS datasets using new reference assemblies

A new GWAS using pseudomolecules from the new FRAX-001 assemblies identified 790 SNPs significantly associated with ADB resistance (Figure 1). This showed 115 genes annotated by the liftover were within 5kb of these SNPs, two of which were also within 5kb of a significant SNP from the (Stocks et al. 2019) study. Two hundred and twenty four genes from the *de novo* annotation were within 5kb of a significant SNP. This indicates that a more contiguous genome allows identification of additional genes potentially associated with ADB resistance, and that the reference genome used for a GWAS can significantly impact which genes are identified as being associated with a trait.

The genomic liftover of previous GWAS results (Stocks et al. 2019) assigned 2.2 million of the 9.3 million SNPs from this study to chromosomes in the FRAX-001 assembly. The associated p-values from Stocks et al. are displayed in Figure 2. Comparison of Figures 1 and 2 show that in some cases (e.g. chromosome 16) significant ADB associations identified from mapping to one reference genome are not recovered when mapping to

another reference genome. Mapping errors to one or indeed both the assemblies are likely responsible for these inconsistencies, potentially due to structural variation between the genomes sequenced to produce the reference assemblies.

Figure 1: Genome Wide Association Study of Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms from read mapping to FRAX-001 assembly. The $-\log_{10}$ transformed of the p-value resulting from a Cochran-Mantel-Haenszel test, testing an association with ash dieback disease resistance status across 15 populations, is plotted on the y-axis, with their position in the genome reported on the x-axis, with each chromosome represented by a number. Alternating colours represent the different chromosomes.

Figure 2: P-values from Genome Wide Association Study of Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms on BATG-0.5 assembly lifted to FRAX-001 assembly. Sites tested for ADB association when mapped to the BATG-0.5 genome assembly were lifted over to the FRAX-001 assembly. The $-\log_{10}$ transformed of the p-value from the Cochran-Mantel-Haenszel test in the original GWAS (testing an association with ash dieback disease resistance status across 15 populations) are displayed. Position in the FRAX-001 assembly is reported on the x-axis, with each chromosome represented by a number. Alternating colours represent the different chromosomes. Chromosome are plotted in the same order as in Figure 1.

Analysis of the contribution of structural variants to ash dieback resistance

The FRAX-001 assembly was used to investigate structural variants associated with ADB resistance. This approach identified 12,177 well-supported tandem repeats across the 23 chromosomes from the pooled field trial data. Each tandem repeat was a median distance of 12bp from the nearest genotyped SNP. Proxies of genotype frequency across the pooled data were estimated and used to perform a GWAS across the 15 populations for association with ADB resistance (Figure 3). The most significant 1% of SVs from the GWAS similarly had a median distance of 16bp from the nearest genotyped SNP. However, they were on average 2.3Mb away from the nearest SNP that was significantly differentiated in the SNP-based GWAS, with the closest still being 97kb away. This suggests that genetic variation in SNPs and nearby SVs may not be sufficiently correlated to identify highly differentiated SVs from SNP data alone, justifying the current approach. The most significant 1% of SVs were within 5kb of 55 genes identified from the *de novo* annotation. One of these genes showed homology to a sieve-element occlusion c-like protein: these proteins are involved in repairing phloem damage, and may represent a mechanism for resistance to severe ADB infection. These results justified the further investigation of SVs in ADB resistance via the “Transforming ash genomics” project within the CFP, and have also been used as pilot data in a proposal to NERC to further investigate SVs in ash disease resistance.

Figure 3: Genome Wide Association Study of Tandem Duplicates across 15 populations. Tandem duplicates are plotted by their position in the genome reported on the x-axis, with each chromosome represented by a number. Alternating colours represent the different chromosomes. The position on the y-axis represents the $-\log_{10}$ transformed p-value resulting from a Cochran-Mantel-Haenszel test, testing an association between the proportion of reads at a locus associated with a structural variant (SV) with ash dieback disease resistance status across 15 accessions.

Conclusions

We have successfully completed the analysis of data previously collected from a natural ash woodland, and conclusions from this study can be found in the submitted manuscript. Ash genome data has been made more accessible to the public. Our various analyses of the new ash reference genome and our previously generated field trial data demonstrate that discovery of SNPs associated with ash dieback resistance is highly reference-dependent. The contiguity of the new assembly, and the fact that it was generated from a Polish tree, both likely contribute to the different SNPs identified when we use it as a basis for a GWAS. Our preliminary analyses of SVs in ash suggest that these are also involved in ash dieback resistance. In order to improve our knowledge of SNP and SV based resistance to ash dieback, and more fully understand the genetic basis of ash dieback

resistance, a pan-genome is needed for ash. A pan-genome is a reference which incorporates the breadth of structural diversity across a species (Lei et al. 2021). This work is now being done by a project funded under the 2022-2025 Centre for Forest Protection research plan, entitled: “Transforming ash genomics: a pan-genome resource for improved understanding of ash dieback resistance”.

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